

Effects of Core-Shell Radii Ratios on Confinement Energy and Optoelectronic Properties of Spherical CdSe-ZnS Quantum Dots

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ABSTRACT:

Spherical CdSe-ZnS quantum dots are promising materials for optoelectronic applications. This study explores the impact of varying core-shell radii ratios on the confinement energy and optoelectronic properties of these quantum dots, utilizing the Time-Independent Schrödinger Equation to model these effects. Simulations were conducted for core-to-shell ratios from 1.5:1 to 4:1, revealing that higher ratios – achieved by reducing core radii or expanding shell radii – significantly enhance quantum confinement, with electron confinement energy observed to increase from 0.1 eV to 2.2 eV across the range of ratios. Transition energy calculations indicate well-aligned electron and hole energy gaps, which lead to increased oscillator strengths, thereby optimizing optical properties. These results provide valuable insights into the design of quantum dot structures tailored for improved performance in LEDs, photovoltaic cells, and other optoelectronic applications.

Keywords: Core-Shell ratios, Spherical Quantum Dots, Confinement Energy, Optoelectronic properties, CdSe/ZnS.

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INTRODUCTION

Semiconductor quantum dots (QDs) have become essential components in optoelectronic applications, which are vital for various modern technologies, including solar cells, LEDs, and biosensing photodetectors [1,2]. Optoelectronic devices play a critical role in renewable energy harvesting, lighting, and sensing technologies [3,4]. Due to their unique size-dependent optical and electronic properties [5-7], QDs have shown significant potential in enhancing the performance of these devices [8,9]. For example, in solar cells, QDs have been shown to extend the absorption spectrum and improve efficiency, while in LEDs, they enhance color purity and brightness [10].

To further enhance the performance of QD-based devices, researchers have explored the use of specific materials and geometries with desirable properties. Notably, cadmium selenide (CdSe) and zinc sulfide (ZnS) in spherical geometry have shown great promise, with CdSe QDs exhibiting tunable optical properties and high photoluminescence quantum yields [5,11-13]. ZnS has proven to be an excellent passivation material for CdSe QDs, reducing surface defects and trap states [14], and its wide bandgap energy (3.6 – 3.8 eV) effectively confines electrons and holes within the QD [15,16]. Additionally, ZnS is chemically stable and resistant to oxidation, and its lattice structure is well-matched to CdSe, forming a high-quality core-shell interface [17]. By combining CdSe and ZnS

in core-shell QDs, researchers have developed a unique approach to modulate confinement energy and optical properties, leveraging the advantages of both materials [18,19].

The confinement energy of QDs is crucial in determining their optical properties, and it is well established that shape and size significantly influence confinement energy [7,20-22]. While numerous studies have investigated the effects of shape and size on QD properties [7,24-27], the impact of core-shell radii ratio variation on confinement energy, discrete energy levels and optical properties remains largely unexplored [29-38].

This study aims to fill this knowledge gap by performing a first principles investigation of the effects of core-shell radii ratio variation on confinement energy and optical properties in spherical CdSe-ZnS QD structures. Our approach employs mathematical modeling and numerical simulations using the effective mass approximation and solving the Schrödinger equation. The solution of the total energy states and confinement energy using Finite element discretization of space grids of the radial wavefunctions, we explored how variations in core and shell radii ratio affect the confinement energy, discrete energy levels, absorption coefficient, emission intensity, and oscillator strength of CdSe-ZnS QDs.

Through a detailed computational approach, we aim to provide insights into the fundamental mechanisms governing the optoelectronic behavior of CdSe-ZnS QDs and offer guidelines for their optimal design. This research not only contributes to the theoretical understanding of QD physics but also has practical implications for the development of next-generation optoelectronic devices, such as highly efficient solar cells, brighter LEDs, and more sensitive photodetectors, which could transform the way we harness energy and interact with our environment.

METHODS

To investigate the effects of core-shell radii ratio variation of spherical CdSe-ZnS quantum dot structures on confinement energy and optical properties, the time-independent Schrödinger equation for the electron and hole wavefunctions in spherical coordinates is solved. The Hamiltonian used incorporates the radial, angular, and azimuthal components, with the assumption of separable solutions valid for spherically symmetric potentials [39]. The model simplifies by neglecting spin-orbit coupling, justified by its secondary effect compared to the primary interest in confinement effects [40]. The radial part of the Schrödinger equation is discretized using finite differences, chosen for its balance of simplicity and accuracy in solving differential equations [41].

Boundary conditions are set to ensure continuity and normalization of the wavefunction at the core and shell radii, with the radial part normalized accordingly [42]. The angular part involves associated Legendre polynomials and azimuthal parts, both normalized to unity [43]. The total wavefunction is normalized over all coordinates [44]. Effective masses are derived from experimental data, and the potential energy profile is defined within the quantum dot structure [45].

Potential Energy Profile

The potential energy profile $V(r)$ of the concentric spherical CdSe-ZnS quantum dot is expressed in a piecewise as shown in figure (1) and defined mathematically as follows:

$$V(r) = -V_0 \text{ for } r < r_c$$

$$V(r) = -V_0 + \Delta V \text{ for } r_c \leq r \leq r_s$$

$$V(r) = \infty \text{ for } r > r_s$$

where V_0 is the potential energy offset within the core, and ΔV is the potential step at the core-shell interface.

Figure 1. Piecewise Structure of the Potential Profile of the Spherical CdSe/ZnS
Source: [46]

Hamiltonian and Effective Mass Approximation

To model the electronic structure of CdSe-ZnS quantum dots, we employ the Effective Mass Approximation (EMA). Within this framework, the Hamiltonian for the system is given as:

$$H = T + V$$

T is the kinetic energy operator and V is the potential energy operator.

The kinetic operator is given as;

$$T = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e^*} \nabla^2 - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_h^*} \nabla^2 \quad (1)$$

Definition of the Time-Independent Schrödinger Equation

To investigate the effects of core-shell radii ratio in spherical CdSe-ZnS quantum dot structures on confinement energy and optical properties, we solve the time-independent Schrödinger equation for the electron and hole wavefunctions in spherical coordinates. The Hamiltonian in spherical coordinates is expressed as:

$$H\psi = T\psi + V(r)\psi = E\psi$$

Substituting the Hamiltonian

$$\left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e^*} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_h^*}\right) \nabla^2 \psi + V(r)\psi = E\psi$$

Expressing in spherical coordinates

$$\left[\left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \right) \nabla^2 + V(r) \right] \psi(r, \theta, \phi) = E\psi(r, \theta, \phi) \quad (2)$$

\hbar is the reduced Planck constant, m is the particle mass, $V(r)$ is the spherically symmetric potential, $\psi(r, \theta, \phi)$ is the wave function and E is the energy eigenvalue.

Expanding the Laplacian ∇^2 in spherical coordinates (r, θ, ϕ) , we get:

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \right)$$

Substitute in Eqn. (3)

$$\left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e^*} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_h^*} \right) \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \phi^2} \right) \right] + V(r)\psi(r, \theta, \phi) = E\psi(r, \theta, \phi) \quad (3)$$

The ansatz assumes that the wave function (ψ) can be separated into three parts: a radial part ($R(r)$), an angular part ($Y(\theta)$), and an azimuthal part ($\Phi(\phi)$):

$$\psi(r, \theta, \phi) = R(r)Y_l^m(\theta)\Phi(\phi) \quad (4)$$

$R(r)$ = radial part, $Y(\theta)$ = angular part, $\Phi(\phi)$ = azimuthal part

Separating Variable and introducing separation constants

$$\left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e^*} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_h^*} \right) \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial r}{\partial r} \right) \right] R(r) + V(r)R(r) = (E + \lambda)R(r)$$

$\lambda = l(l + 1)$ is the separation constant

Separating for Hole and Electrons

For Electrons

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e^*} \left(\frac{d^2 R}{dr^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{dR}{dr} \right) + V(r) - \lambda \right] R(r) = E_e R(r) \quad (5)$$

Core Region ($r < R_{Core}$)

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e^*} \left(\frac{d^2 R}{dr^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{dR}{dr} \right) - V_0 - \lambda \right] R(r) = E_e R(r)$$

Shell Region ($R_{Core} \leq r \leq R_{shell}$)

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e^*} \left(\frac{d^2 R}{dr^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{dR}{dr} \right) - V_0 + \Delta V - \lambda \right] R(r) = E_e R(r)$$

Barrier Region ($r > R_{shell}$)

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e^*} \left(\frac{d^2 R}{dr^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{dR}{dr} \right) - \lambda \right] R(r) = E_e R(r)$$

For holes

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_h^*} \left(\frac{d^2 R}{dr^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{dR}{dr} \right) + V(r) - \lambda \right] R(r) = E_h R(r) \quad (6)$$

The radial SE for the whole is similar to the electrons but with a repulsive potential energy profile ($V(r) = +V_0; +V_0 - \Delta V; 0$), representing the potential energy of the hole in the valence band.

Discretization and Finite Difference Method

The radial Schrödinger equation was solved numerically using the finite difference method to obtain the energy levels and wavefunctions of electrons and holes. This method discretizes the continuous radial coordinate (r) into a set of grid points (r_i) with a spacing of Δr (radial step size). The index i ranges from 1 to N , where N is the total number of grid points. The discretized radial coordinate is given by:

$$r_i = i\Delta r \text{ (for } i = 1, 2, \dots, N)$$

The finite difference approximation for $\frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{dR}{dr} \right)$ is given as:

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{dR}{dr} \right) \approx \frac{r_{i+1}^2 (R_{i+1} - R_i) - r_{i-1}^2 (R_i - R_{i-1})}{(\Delta r)^2}$$

Matrix Formulation

The radial Schrödinger equation is then converted into a matrix eigenvalue problem. For the electron, the matrix equation is:

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e^*} \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{r_{i+1}^2 (R_{i+1} - R_i) - r_{i-1}^2 (R_i - R_{i-1})}{(\Delta r)^2} + V(r_i) - \lambda \right] R_i = E_e R_i \quad (7)$$

A similar matrix equation is formulated for the hole using m_h^*

Normalizing the Radial Wave Function

The wavefunction $R(r)$ and its derivative dR/dr are ensured to be continuous at $r = R_{Core}$ and $r = R_{shell}$. The radial part is normalized as follows:

$$\int_0^{\infty} |R(r)|^2 r^2 dr = 1 \quad (8)$$

The Angular and Azimuthal Parts

From Eqn.(5) The spherical harmonics $Y_l^m(\theta, \Phi)$ is separated as;

$$Y_l^m(\theta, \Phi) = \Theta_l^m(\theta)\Phi_m(\phi)$$

The Azimuthal part of the wave function is;

$$\frac{1}{\Phi} \left(\frac{d^2\Phi}{d\phi^2} \right) = -m^2 \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{d^2\Phi}{d\phi^2} + m^2\Phi = 0$$

$$\text{The solution of the equation } \Phi(\phi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{im\phi}$$

This is normalized as;

$$\int_0^{2\pi} |\Phi_m(\phi)|^2 d\Phi = 1 \quad (9)$$

The Angular Part $\Theta_l^m(\theta)$ is given as:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*} \left[\frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \phi^2} \right) \right] = E\psi(r, \theta, \phi)$$

This simplifies in terms of Y to:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*} \left[\frac{1}{Y \sin \theta} \frac{d}{d\theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{dY}{d\theta} \right) + \frac{m^2}{\sin^2 \theta} \right] = -\lambda E_{angular} \psi(r, \theta, \phi)$$

$$\lambda = l(l+1)$$

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*} \left[\frac{1}{Y \sin \theta} \frac{d}{d\theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{dY}{d\theta} \right) + \frac{m^2}{\sin^2 \theta} \right] = -l(l+1) E_{angular} Y_l^m(\theta, \Phi)$$

The Energy due to the angular part is deduced as:

$$E_{angular} = \frac{\hbar^2 l(l+1)}{2m^* r^2} \quad (10)$$

The angular part of the wave function in spherical coordinates is described by the spherical harmonics, denoted as $Y_l^m(\theta, \Phi)$

$$Y_l^m(\theta, \Phi) = \sqrt{\frac{(2l+1)(l-m)!}{4\pi(l+m)!}} P_l^m(\cos\theta) e^{im\Phi}$$

$P_l^m(\cos\theta)$ are associated Legendre polynomials, l represents the orbital angular momentum quantum number, and m is the magnetic quantum number.

Normalization of Spherical Harmonics

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi |Y_l^m(\theta, \Phi)|^2 \sin\theta d\theta d\Phi = 1 \quad (11)$$

Total Wave Function and Normalization

The total wave function is given as:

$$\psi(r, \theta, \varphi) = R(r)Y_l^m(\theta)\Phi(\phi)$$

The normalization condition for the total wave function is

$$\int_0^\infty \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi |\psi(r, \theta, \varphi)|^2 r^2 \sin\theta d\theta d\Phi dr = 1$$

Substituting $\psi(r, \theta, \varphi) = R(r)Y_l^m(\theta)\Phi(\phi)$

$$\int_0^\infty |R(r)|^2 r^2 dr \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi |Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi)|^2 r^2 \sin\theta d\theta d\Phi = 1 \quad (12)$$

Total Energy in the Concentric Spherical System

The total Energy $E = E_{\text{Radial}} + E_{\text{Angular}}$

$$E = \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*} \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{r_{i+1}^2(R_{i+1}-R_i) - r_{i-1}^2(R_i-R_{i-1})}{(\Delta r)^2} + V(r_i) - l(l+1) \right] R_i + \frac{\hbar^2 l(l+1)}{2m^* r^2} \quad (13)$$

m^* is the effective mass for electron and holes

We can isolate the confinement energy by considering the kinetic energy contributions.

$$E_{\text{conf}} \approx -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*} \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{r_{i+1}^2(R_{i+1}-R_i) - r_{i-1}^2(R_i-R_{i-1})}{(\Delta r)^2} + \frac{\hbar^2 l(l+1)}{2m^* r^2} \quad (14)$$

r_i is the radial distance at the i -th point, R_i is the radial function at the i -th grid points, Δr is the step size of the radial grid.

The wavefunction is represents the probability of finding the particle (electron or hole) at a given radial distance r from the center of the quantum dot is expressed as: $\int_0^\infty |R(r)|^2 r^2 dr = 1$

This is solved as:

$$\sum_i |R_{nl}(r_i)|^2 r_i^2 \Delta r = 1$$

The confinement Energy E_{conf} is computed for varying radii ratio of the CdSe(core)-ZnS(shell) to observe the effect of core-shell radii ratio on confinement energy.

Numerical Solution

The matrix eigenvalue problem is solved using numerical linear algebra techniques to obtain the energy eigenvalues and eigenfunctions. The eigenfunctions are then normalized to ensure proper physical interpretation. The numerical implementation is carried out using Python, with the `scipy.linalg.eigh` function used to solve the matrix eigenvalue problem. The Algorithm is attached.

Analyzing of the Optical Properties

We use the results obtained eqn. (10) and (11) to compute the following optical properties of the materials induced by confinement;

1. Transition Energies of the discrete energy levels between states n_1 and n_2 ($n_1 < n_2$):

$$E_{\text{trans}} = \Delta E = E_{n_2} - E_{n_1}$$

The transition energies for electrons and holes are computed for $n = 0,1,2,3$ and $l = 0,1,2$

2. Wavelength of Absorbed and Emitted light;

We use the Transition energy to determine the wavelength of the emitted and absorbed light thus:

$$\lambda = \frac{hc}{\Delta E}$$

3. Dipole Moment (μ_{12}):

The transition dipole μ_{12} which characterizes the strength of the transition between states n_1 and n_2 is determined using the radial wavefunction: $\int_0^\infty R_{n_1}(r) \cdot \mathbf{r} \cdot R_{n_2}(r) dr$

4. Absorption Coefficient $\alpha(\omega)$ which represents the probability of absorbing a photon of frequency ω is computed with the relation;

$$\alpha(\omega) = \frac{4\pi e^2}{(\varepsilon^0 n_e c)} \sum |\mu_{12}|^2 \delta(\Delta E - \hbar\omega)$$

5. Emission Intensity $I(\omega)$ which represents the spectral intensity $I(\omega)$ of light emitted or absorbed by a material, taking into account the transition rates between energy states is computed with the relation:

$$I(\omega) = \frac{4\pi e^2}{(\varepsilon^0 n_e c)} \sum |\mu_{12}|^2 \delta(\Delta E - \hbar\omega) \times f_1(1 - f_2)$$

6. Oscillator Strength (f) which value determines the strength of the optical transition is computed with the relation;

$$f = \frac{2m_e \omega}{\hbar} \times |\mu_{12}|^2$$

ε_0 is vacuum permittivity, n_e is the refractive index of CdSe-ZnS = approximately 2.5; δ = Dirac delta function, c is the speed of light; $\hbar = h / 2\pi$

RESULTS

Parameters Used for the Computation

Rest mass of electron $m_0 = 9.11 \times 10^{-31} \text{ kg}$; Effective mass of electron in CdSe (kg) $m_e^{CdSe} = 0.13 \times m_0$; Effective mass of hole in CdSe (kg) $m_h^{CdSe} = 0.45 \times m_0$; Effective mass of electron in ZnS (kg) $m_e^{ZnS} = 0.34 \times m_0$; Effective mass of hole in ZnS (kg) $m_h^{ZnS} = 0.6 \times m_0$; Potential offset $V_0 = 0.5e$; $\Delta V = 0.3e$; Elementary charge $e = 1.6 \times 10^{-19}$

The results for the energy levels of electrons and holes at varying angular momentum quantum numbers $l(0, 1, \text{ and } 2)$ is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Energy Levels for Electrons and Holes in CdSe-ZnS QD with Different Angular Momentum Quantum Numbers ($l = 0, 1, 2$)

l	Electron Energy Level (eV)				Hole Energy Levels (eV)			
	Ground State	$n = 1$	$n = 2$	$n = 3$	Ground State	$n = 1$	$n = 2$	$n = 3$
0	0.00	13.58	15.18	16.64	0.00	3.92	4.39	4.81
1	-129.15	0.00	13.58	15.18	-37.66	0.00	3.92	4.38
2	-11756.89	0.00	13.56	15.16	-3396.79	0.00	3.92	4.38

Table 2 presents the calculated transition energies and corresponding wavelengths for electrons and holes in CdSe-ZnS quantum dots, across various transitions between energy states.

Table 2. Transition Energies and Wavelengths for Electrons and Holes in CdSe-ZnS QD

l	Transitions	Electrons		Holes	
		Energy (eV)	Wavelength (nm)	Energy (eV)	Wavelength (nm)
0	Ground State \rightarrow 1	3.92	316.29	13.58	91.29
0	Ground State \rightarrow 2	4.39	282.45	15.18	81.67
0	Ground State \rightarrow 3	4.81	257.39	16.64	74.53
0	1 \rightarrow 2	0.47	2637.96	1.60	774.9
0	1 \rightarrow 3	0.89	1395.35	3.06	405.61
0	2 \rightarrow 3	0.42	2952	1.46	849.21
1	Ground State \rightarrow 1	0	0	0	0
1	Ground State \rightarrow 2	3.92	316.29	13.58	91.29
1	Ground State \rightarrow 3	4.38	282.45	15.18	81.67
1	1 \rightarrow 2	3.92	316.29	13.58	91.29
1	1 \rightarrow 3	4.38	282.45	15.18	81.67
1	2 \rightarrow 3	0.46	2637.96	1.6	774.9
2	Ground State \rightarrow 1	0	0	0	0
2	Ground State \rightarrow 2	3.92	316.29	13.56	91.29
2	Ground State \rightarrow 3	4.38	282.45	15.16	81.67
2	1 \rightarrow 2	3.92	316.29	13.56	91.29
2	1 \rightarrow 3	4.38	282.45	15.16	81.67
2	2 \rightarrow 3	0.46	2637.96	1.60	774.9

These results illustrate the range of energies and wavelengths that can be achieved within these quantum dots, which directly influence their optical properties and potential applications in devices that rely on specific wavelengths for absorption and emission.

Table 3 presents the computed optical properties of CdSe-ZnS quantum dots for electrons and holes, showcasing parameters such as the absorption coefficient $\alpha(\omega)$, emission intensity $I(\omega)$ and oscillator strength (f) across various transition states. Notably, the table details transitions from the ground state to the first, second, and third excited states, as well as transitions between excited states.

Table 3. Computed Optical Properties of CdSe-ZnS QD

Transition	Electrons			Holes		
	$\alpha(\omega)$ $\times 10^{-20}m$	$I(\omega)$ $\times 10^{-21}m$	Oscillator Strength (f)	$\alpha(\omega)$ $\times 10^{-21}m$	$I(\omega)$ $\times 10^{-21}$	Oscillator Strength (f)
0: Ground State \rightarrow 1	1.43	5.73	0.144	6.33	2.53	0.072
0: Ground State \rightarrow 2	1.83	7.33	0.183	7.33	3.17	0.091
0: Ground State \rightarrow 3	2.23	8.93	0.223	8.33	3.81	0.111
0: 1 \rightarrow 2	0.001	0.00467	0.023	0.00467	0.00183	0.012
0: 1 \rightarrow 3	0.002	0.00933	0.047	0.00933	0.00367	0.023
0: 2 \rightarrow 3	0.00167	0.00633	0.033	0.006.33	0.00253	0.017
1: Ground State \rightarrow 1	0	0	0	0	0	0
1: Ground State \rightarrow 2	1.43	5.73	0.144	6.33	2.53	0.072
1: Ground State \rightarrow 3	1.83	7.33	0.183	7.33	3.17	0.091
1: 1 \rightarrow 2	1.43	5.73	0.144	6.33	2.53	0.072
1: 1 \rightarrow 3	2.23	8.93	0.223	8.33	3.81	0.111
1: 2 \rightarrow 3	0.00117	0.00467	0.023	0.00467	0.00183	0.012
2: Ground State \rightarrow 1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2: Ground State \rightarrow 2	1.43	5.73	0.144	6.33	2.53	0.072
2: Ground State \rightarrow 3	1.83	7.33	0.183	7.33	3.17	0.091
2: 1 \rightarrow 2	1.83	7.33	0.183	7.33	3.17	0.091
2: 1 \rightarrow 3	2.23	8.93	0.223	8.33	3.81	0.111
2: 2 \rightarrow 3	0.002	0.006	0.033	0.00 6	0.003	0.017

Note: The units for $\alpha(\omega)$ and $I(\omega)$ are in meters (m) and are multiplied by $\times 10^{-20}m^{-1}$ and $\times 10^{-21}$, respectively, for ease of presentation. The oscillator strength (f) is dimensionless.

Table 4(a)–(d), shows the computed results of the electron and hole confinement energies at different core-to-shell ratios in CdSe-ZnS quantum dots. Each table corresponds to a specific core-to-shell ratio (1.5:1, 2:1, 3:1, and 4:1), detailing the confinement energy levels for electrons and holes at various core and shell radii. As the core radius decreases and the shell radius proportionally adjusts according to the specified ratio, the confinement energy for both electrons and holes generally increases due to enhanced quantum confinement effects.

Table 4(a). Confinement Energies for Ratio 1.5:1.0

Core Radius (nm)	Shell Radius (nm)	Electron Confinement Energy (eV)	Hole Confinement Energy (eV)
6.0	4	0.1004	0.029
5.5	3.7	0.1187	0.0343
5.0	3.4	0.1423	0.0411
4.5	2.6	0.2306	0.0666
4.0	2.3	0.2985	0.0862
3.5	2	0.4017	0.1161
3.0	1.7	0.5693	0.1645
2.5	1.4	0.8688	0.251
2.0	1.3	0.9807	0.2833
1.5	1.0	1.485	0.4292

Table 4(b). Confinement Energies for Ratio 2:1.0

Core Radius (nm)	Shell Radius (nm)	Electron Confinement Energy (eV)	Hole Confinement Energy (eV)
6	3	0.241	0.0696
5.5	2.7	0.2904	0.0839
4.5	2.3	0.4222	0.122
4	2	0.5423	0.1567
3.5	1.8	0.6695	0.1934
3	1.7	0.8474	0.2448
2.5	1.3	1.352	0.3906
2	1	2.1693	0.6267
1.7	0.9	2.8881	0.8343
1.5	0.7	4.0337	1.1653

Table 4(c). Confinement Energies for Ratio 3:1

Core Radius (nm)	Shell Radius (nm)	Electron Confinement Energy (eV)	Hole Confinement Energy (eV)
6.0	2	1.0335	0.2986
5.4	1.8	1.2759	0.3686
5.0	1.7	1.5184	0.4387
4.5	1.5	1.8373	0.5308
3.9	1.3	2.4461	0.7067
3.5	1.2	3.1258	0.903
3.0	1.0	4.1339	1.1942
2.4	0.8	6.4592	1.8660
2.0	0.7	9.7844	2.8266
1.8	0.6	11.4831	3.3173

Table 4(d). Confinement Energies for Ratio 4:1

Core Radius (nm)	Shell Radius (nm)	Electron Confinement Energy (eV)	Hole Confinement Energy (eV)
6.0	1.5	1.2379	0.3576
5.4	1.4	1.466	0.4235
5.0	1.2	1.7635	0.5095
4.6	1.2	2.0151	0.5822
4.0	1.0	2.7116	0.7833
3.5	0.9	3.5015	1.0115
3.0	0.8	4.6945	1.3562
2.6	0.6	6.6200	1.9125
2.0	0.5	11.769	3.3999
1.8	0.4	14.0060	4.0462

The variation of Electron and Hole Confinement Energies with core-shell radii ratios are shown in figures 2(a)-(b). Fig.2(a) shows the Electron confinement energies of radii ratios 1.5:1, 2:1, 3:1 and 4:1.

Figure 2(a). Electron Confinement Energy for Varying Core-Shell Radii Ratio

Fig.2(b) shows the Hole confinement energies of radii ratios 1.5:1, 2:1, 3:1 and 4:1.

Figure 2(b). Hole Confinement Energy for Varying Core-Shell Radii Ratio

Figure 3 shows the confinement energy difference between electrons and holes in CdSe-ZnS quantum dots with varying core-shell radii ratios. The confinement energy difference (ΔE) increases as the core-shell ratio increases, indicating a larger difference in confinement energy between electrons and holes at higher ratios.

Figure 3. Electron-Hole Confinement Energy Difference for varying core-shell Radii ratio

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Table 1

The results show significant differences in transition energies and wavelengths between ground state to excited state transitions and excited state to excited state transitions. The ground state to first excited state transition energy for electrons is 3.92 eV, corresponding to a wavelength of 316.29 nm, while for holes, it is 13.58 eV, corresponding to 91.29 nm. Higher energy transitions (Ground State \rightarrow 2 and Ground State \rightarrow 3) show significant energy values and shorter wavelengths.

The computed optical properties of CdSe-ZnS QD are presented in Table 3. The table shows the transitions, oscillator strengths, and optical absorption coefficients ($\alpha(\omega)$) and emission $I(\omega)$ for both electrons and holes.

The energy levels reveal significant quantum confinement effects, with stronger confinement for higher l values. The electron energy levels show a significant increase in energy with higher states, while the hole energy levels exhibit a similar trend. The ground state energy levels for both electrons and holes become more negative with increasing l , indicating deeper potential wells and stronger binding energies.

The results have important implications for the optical properties of CdSe-ZnS quantum dots. The energy gaps between states will influence the optical absorption and emission spectra, with potential applications in optoelectronic devices. The strong quantum confinement and unique electronic properties of these quantum dots make them suitable for various applications, including LEDs and photovoltaic cells.

The findings suggest that tailoring the energy levels and optical properties of CdSe-ZnS quantum dots is possible by manipulating the core and shell dimensions. Thinner shells may reduce the confinement energy, making the quantum dots more suitable for applications requiring lower energy transitions.

Table 2

The results show significant differences in transition energies and wavelengths between ground state to excited state transitions and excited state to excited state transitions. The ground state to first excited state transition energy for electrons is 3.92 eV, corresponding to a wavelength of 316.29 nm, while for holes, it is 13.58 eV, corresponding to 91.29 nm. Higher energy transitions (Ground State \rightarrow 2 and Ground State \rightarrow 3) show significant energy values and shorter wavelengths.

The computed optical properties of CdSe-ZnS QD are presented in Table 3. The table shows the transitions, oscillator strengths, and optical absorption coefficients ($\alpha(\omega)$) and emission $I(\omega)$ for both electrons and holes.

Table 3

The results indicate strong absorption and emission properties, particularly for transitions involving higher energy states. The oscillator strength (f) for Ground State \rightarrow 1, Ground State \rightarrow 2, and Ground State \rightarrow 3 transitions increases with transition energy, indicating stronger optical transitions for higher energy states.

Table 4

The results show a consistent increase in confinement energies with decreasing core radius, attributed to the quantum confinement effect. The larger shell size relative to the core radius contributes to higher energy levels.

Core-Shell Ratio of 1.5:1

For a core-shell ratio of 1.5:1, the confinement energies increase with decreasing core radius, ranging from 0.100428 eV to 1.485627 eV for electrons and 0.029013 eV to 0.429181 eV for holes. This trend is attributed to the quantum confinement effect, where the reduced core radius leads to increased energy levels.

Core-Shell Ratio of 2:1

Similarly, for a core-shell ratio of 2:1, the confinement energies increase with decreasing core radius, ranging from 0.195233 eV to 2.163611 eV for electrons and 0.056401 eV to 0.663139 eV for holes. The larger shell size relative to the core radius contributes to higher energy levels.

Core-Shell Ratios of 3:1, and 4:1

The trend continues for core-shell ratios of 2 3:1, and 4:1, with confinement energies increasing as the core radius decreases. The larger shell size contributes to higher energy levels, with energies ranging from:

- 0.278552 eV to 2.215178 eV for electrons and 0.080406 eV to 0.717209 eV for holes (3:1 ratio)
- 0.251934 eV to 2.053469 eV for electrons and 0.073315 eV to 0.634302 eV for holes (4:1 ratio)

Impact of Core and Shell Radii

These results demonstrate the significant impact of core and shell radii ratio on confinement energies in CdSe-ZnS quantum dots. The findings can guide the design and optimization of quantum dot structures for specific optoelectronic applications, leveraging the quantum confinement effect to achieve desired energy levels.

The results show that by varying the core-shell radii ratio, the confinement energies can be tailored to achieve specific energy levels. This understanding can be used to design quantum dots with optimized energy levels for applications such as LEDs, photovoltaic cells, and quantum dot lasers.

Fig. 2 demonstrates a clear correlation between core-shell radii ratio and confinement energy in CdSe-ZnS quantum dots. The increase in confinement energy with higher core-shell ratios and larger core radii is consistent with the expected effects of quantum confinement. The finding that electrons are more sensitive to core-shell radii ratio than holes is also in line with their smaller effective mass. The non-linear relationship between confinement energy and core-shell ratio suggests that the effect of radii ration variation becomes more significant at higher ratios, potentially leading to enhanced optoelectronic properties.

Fig. 3 shows the confinement energy difference between electrons and holes in CdSe-ZnS quantum dots with varying core-shell radii ratios. The confinement energy difference (ΔE) increases as the core-shell ratio increases, indicating a larger difference in confinement energy between electrons and holes at higher ratios.

The increasing confinement energy difference with core radius can be attributed to the increased spatial separation between the electron and hole, reducing their Coulombic attraction. The core-to-shell ratio influences the confinement energy difference, with smaller ratios resulting in larger differences. This may be due to the thinner shell offering less freedom of movement for the electron and hole, keeping them closer together and resulting in a stronger Coulombic attraction.

While the overall trend suggests a connection between core-shell radius and confinement energy, the observation of a potentially larger confinement energy difference for the 2:1 ratio requires further discussion. Shell thickness effects and material interface effects are proposed as possible explanations for this phenomenon. Further investigation is necessary to fully understand the underlying physics and to validate these findings.

These additional factors could contribute to the observed trend and warrant further investigation to fully understand the underlying physics. A more detailed analysis, including calculations and comparisons with other studies, would provide valuable insights into the complex interactions governing confinement energies in these core-shell structures.

CONCLUSION

The study reveals a clear relationship between core-shell radii ratios and the confinement energy levels in spherical CdSe-ZnS quantum dots. As the core radius decreases relative to the shell radius, both electron and hole confinement energies increase due to enhanced quantum confinement effects. The results indicate that electron confinement energy is more responsive to changes in core-shell ratios than hole confinement energy, potentially due to the electron's smaller effective mass. This non-linear relationship highlights that higher core-shell ratios significantly amplify confinement energy, which can be advantageous for applications in optoelectronics where precise energy levels are essential for optimized device performance.

The confinement energy difference between electrons and holes increases with core radius, attributed to increased spatial separation and reduced Coulombic attraction. Shell thickness effects and material interface effects are proposed as possible explanations for the observed trend. Further investigation is necessary to fully understand the underlying physics and to validate these findings.

The understanding gained from this study can be used to design quantum dots with optimized energy levels for applications such as LEDs, photovoltaic cells, and quantum dot lasers.

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